

Summary of Recommendations

The Fairness and Wellbeing Commission have come up with a series of recommendations to support Doncaster residents:

1

Creating a **fair** and **empowering** future.

1. Doncaster's educational settings should play a leading role within the community, **encouraging civic pride** and **providing skills for life**.
2. Champion **inclusive education** for all of Doncaster's Young People.
3. Give Doncaster's children and young people **a voice in shaping services and policy**.
4. Bridge the gap between **education and employment** in Doncaster.

2

Help to navigate life's **tipping points**

1. Develop an evidence-based approach to **identifying and supporting residents at vulnerable times** in their lives.
2. Build **Inclusive Support Networks** and **Legal Awareness** for a Resilient Community.
3. Develop **trusted, sustainable support** in Doncaster communities.
4. Ensure **safe and healthy living conditions** to improve wellbeing in Doncaster.

3

Tackling **in-work poverty**

1. Tackle **in-work poverty** and **improve job security** for Doncaster residents.
2. Build a **Socially Responsible** Business Community.
3. Create the conditions for **social mobility**.
4. **Improve employment opportunities** in Doncaster, ensuring everyone has a fair chance to **succeed and develop**.

4

Ensuring **equitable access** for all

1. Create **trusted & accessible Community Support Hubs** for enhanced resident health and wellbeing
2. Promote **kindness and compassion** in service delivery
3. Support Doncaster residents' transition into the **digital age**
4. Improve Doncaster's public transport to ensure **equitable access for all**